

TESKARI MATRITSANI VA TENGLAMALAR SISTEMASINI EXCEL DASTURI YORDAMIDA YECHISH

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola oliy matematikaning chiziqli algebra qismiga bag‘ishlangan bo‘lib o‘rganuvchilarga biroz murakkab bo‘lgan teskari matritsani hisoblash, shuningdek bu teskari matritsani tez va oson Excel darduri yordamida topish, chiziqli tenglamalar sistemasini yechishning oson usuli haqida. Ya‘ni qisqa vaqtda ko‘p sonli chiziqli tenglamalar sistemasini teskari matritsa usulida qanday tez yechish mumkinligini o‘rgatishga qaratilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: matritsa, teskari matritsa, determinant, Excel, birgalikda bo‘lgan tenglamalar sistemasini, MINVERSE, Inter, xos bo‘lmagan matritsa.

Аннотация. Статья посвящена разделу линейной алгебры высшей математики и обучает студентов вычислению обратной матрицы достаточно сложной формы, а также быстрому и простому нахождению этой обратной матрицы с помощью Excel, а также простому способу решения системы линейных уравнений. То есть его цель — научить быстро решать системы большого числа линейных уравнений за короткое время, используя метод обратной матрицы.

Ключевые слова: матрица, обратная матрица, определитель, Excel, система одновременных уравнений, МОБР, Интер, невырожденная матрица.

Abstract. This article is dedicated to the linear algebra part of higher mathematics and teaches students how to calculate a somewhat complicated inverse matrix, as well as how to quickly and easily find this inverse matrix using Excel, and an easy way to solve a system of linear equations. That is, it aims to teach how to quickly solve a system of linear equations using the inverse matrix method in a short time.

Key words: matrix, inverse matrix, determinant, Excel, system of simultaneous equations, MINVERSE, Inter, non-unique matrix.

Teskari matritsani topish va chiziqli tenglamalar sistemasini yechishning barcha foydalanadigan matematik ta‘rif va teoremlarni keltirib o‘tamiz va hisoblashlarni ko‘rib chiqamiz.

Xos bo‘lmagan, ya‘ni $|A|$ determinant nol bo‘lmagan, A matritsaning teskari matritsasi

$$A^{-1} = \frac{AdjA}{|A|}$$

formula yordamida hisoblanadi..

Misol. $A = \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 4 & 3 \\ 3 & 5 & 0 \\ 4 & 2 & 5 \end{bmatrix}$ matritsaga A^{-1} teskari matritsa topilsin.

Yechish. Bu matrisa uchun yuqoridagi misolda biriktirilgan matrisa topgan edik. Bu matrisa determinantini hisoblaymiz

$$\begin{aligned} |A| &= 3 \begin{vmatrix} 3 & 5 \\ 4 & 2 \end{vmatrix} - 0 + 5 \begin{vmatrix} 2 & 4 \\ 3 & 5 \end{vmatrix} = \\ &= 3(6 - 20) + 5(10 - 12) = \\ &= 3(-14) + 5(-2) = \\ &= -42 - 10 = -52 \end{aligned}$$

Shuning uchun,

$$\text{Adj}A = \begin{bmatrix} 25 & -14 & -15 \\ -15 & -2 & 9 \\ -12 & 12 & -2 \end{bmatrix}$$

Bo'lgani uchun teskari matrisa quyidagi ko'rinishda bo'ladi

$$A^{-1} = \frac{\text{Adj}A}{|A|} = \frac{\begin{bmatrix} 25 & -14 & -15 \\ -15 & -2 & 9 \\ -12 & 12 & -2 \end{bmatrix}}{-52} = \begin{bmatrix} -0.48 & 0.27 & 0.29 \\ 0.29 & 0.04 & -0.17 \\ 0.27 & -0.23 & 0.04 \end{bmatrix}$$

Bu matrisani hisoblash ko'p vaqt talab etadi, lekin siz bu usul asosiyligini bilishingiz kerak, elektron jadvalda hisoblashdan oldin. Endi misol yordamida har bir etapni aniqlaylik. Sodda uchun 2x2 o'lchovli holni qaraylik.

Ta'rif. A kvadrat matritsaga teskari matritsa deb, shunday A^{-1} matritsaga aytiladiki, uning uchun quyidagi $A \cdot A^{-1} = A^{-1} \cdot A = E$ tenglik o'rinli bo'lsin.

Ta'rif. Agar A matritsa uchun $|A| \neq 0$ bo'lsa, bunday matritsa xos bo'lmagan matritsa, aks holda, ya'ni $|A| = 0$ bo'lsa xos matritsa deyiladi.

Teorema. A kvadrat matritsaga teskari A^{-1} matritsa mavjud va yagona bo'lishi uchun, uning xos bo'lmagan matritsa bo'lishi zarur va yetarlidir.

A -matritsa xos bo'lmagan matritsa bo'lsin, ya'ni $|A| \neq 0$ bo'lsin. U holda

$$A^{-1} = \frac{1}{|A|} \begin{pmatrix} A_{11} & A_{21} & \dots & A_{j1} & \dots & A_{n1} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & \dots & A_{j2} & \dots & A_{n2} \\ A_{1k} & A_{2k} & \dots & A_{jk} & \dots & A_{nk} \\ A_{1n} & A_{2n} & \dots & A_{jn} & \dots & A_{nn} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Misol. $A = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 1 \\ 3 & -5 & 3 \\ 2 & 7 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$ matritsaga teskari matrisani toping..

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Yechish. } |A| &= \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 2 & 1 \\ 3 & -5 & 3 \\ 2 & 7 & -1 \end{vmatrix} = 5 + 12 + 21 + 10 - 21 + 6 = 33. & A_{11} = -16, A_{12} = 9, A_{13} = 31 \\ & & A_{21} = 9, A_{22} = -3, A_{23} = -3 \\ & & A_{31} = 11, A_{32} = 0, A_{33} = -11 \end{aligned}$$

$$A^{-1} = \frac{1}{|A|} \begin{pmatrix} -16 & 9 & 11 \\ 9 & -3 & 0 \\ 31 & -3 & -11 \end{pmatrix} = \frac{1}{33} \begin{pmatrix} -16 & 9 & 11 \\ 9 & -3 & 0 \\ 31 & -3 & -11 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{16}{33} & \frac{3}{11} & \frac{1}{3} \\ \frac{3}{11} & -\frac{1}{11} & 0 \\ \frac{11}{33} & -\frac{1}{11} & -\frac{1}{3} \end{pmatrix}$$

Tenglamalar sistemani matrisaviy usulda yechish

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \dots & a_{1n} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \dots & a_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ a_{m1} & a_{m2} & \dots & a_{mn} \end{pmatrix}, \quad X = \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ \vdots \\ x_n \end{pmatrix}, \quad B = \begin{pmatrix} b_1 \\ b_2 \\ \vdots \\ b_m \end{pmatrix}$$

bu yerda A koeffitsientlar sistema matritsasi, B - ozod hadlar matritsasi deyiladi. U holda berilgan tenglamalar sistemasini quyidagi ko'rinishda yoza olamiz:

$$AX = B$$

Tenglamalar sistemasida tenglamalar soni noma'lumlar soniga teng, ya'ni $m = n$, bo'lsin. Bu holda sistema matritsasi A kvadrat matritsa bo'ladi. Agar $\Delta \neq 0$ bo'lsa, ya'ni A -xos bo'lmagan matritsa bo'lsa, u holda A^{-1} teskari matritsa mavjud bo'ladi, u holda $AX = B$ tenglikdan quyidagilarni hosil qilamiz:

$$A^{-1}(AX) = A^{-1}B \Rightarrow (A^{-1}A)X = A^{-1}B \Rightarrow EX = A^{-1}B \Rightarrow X = A^{-1}B \text{ bu munosabatdan:}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ \vdots \\ x_n \end{pmatrix} = \frac{1}{|A|} \begin{pmatrix} A_{11} & A_{21} & \dots & A_{n1} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & \dots & A_{n2} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ A_{1j} & A_{2j} & \dots & A_{nj} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ A_{1n} & A_{2n} & \dots & A_{nn} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} b_1 \\ b_2 \\ \vdots \\ b_m \end{pmatrix}$$

Oxirgi tenglikdan $x_j = \frac{1}{\Delta} (b_1 A_{1j} + b_2 A_{2j} + \dots + b_n A_{nj}) = \frac{\Delta_j}{\Delta}$, $\Delta_j = \overline{1, n}$ ekanligi kelib chiqadi.

$$\text{Masalan. } \begin{cases} 2x_1 + 3x_2 + 4x_3 = 1 \\ x_1 + 2x_2 + 3x_3 = 0 \\ 3x_1 + 4x_2 + 6x_3 = 1 \end{cases} \text{ tenglamalar sistemasini matritsa usulida yechaylik.}$$

Sistemaga mos asosiy, ozod hadlar va noma'lumlar matrisalari mos ravishda

quyidagicha bo'ladi:

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 3 & 4 & 6 \end{pmatrix}, \quad B = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad X = \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$|A| = 24 + 27 + 16 - 24 - 24 - 1 = 1 \neq 0 \text{ bo'lgani uchun } A^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -2 & 1 \\ 3 & 0 & -2 \\ -2 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \text{ bo'ladi.}$$

U holda,

$$X = A^{-1} \cdot B = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -2 & 1 \\ 3 & 0 & -2 \\ -2 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ -1 \end{pmatrix}$$

Demak, $x_1 = 1, x_2 = 1, x_3 = -1$.

Excel dasturida hisoblash teskari matritsa hisoblash

Teskari matrisani Excel dasturida qulay hisoblash mumkin.

Buning uchun Excel MINVERSE formulasi qo'llaniladi:

- Matritsa kiritiladi.
- teskari matritsa uchun joy ajratiladi.
- ekrannig yuqori bar qismiga:
=MINVERSE (*matritsa o'lchovi*) formulani kiritim
- Ctrl va ENTER klavishlarini birga bosong.

Formula { } figurali qavsda ajratilgan joyda teskari matrisani hisoblab beradi.

Excel yordamida birgalikdagi tenglamalar sistemasini yechish

Qisqa vaqtda ko'p sonli chiziqli tenglamalar sistemasini teskari matritsa usulida qanday tez yechish mumkinligini o'rganamiz. Quyidagi misolda olti noma'lumli oltita tenglamalar sistemasini Excel dasturi yordamida qanday soda va tez yechilishi tushuntiriladi. Shundan so'ng siz bu kabi misollarni Excel dasturi yordamida tez bajarishni bilib olaviz.

Misol.

$$\begin{aligned}4x_1 + x_2 + 2x_3 - 17x_4 - 5x_5 + 8x_6 &= 21 \\8x_1 + 9x_2 + 23x_3 + 15x_4 + 11x_5 + 39x_6 &= 593 \\24x_1 + 41x_2 + 9x_3 + 3x_4 + x_6 &= 317 \\6x_1 + 5x_2 - x_4 + 3x_5 + 7x_6 &= 35 \\9x_1 + 11x_2 + 39x_3 + 23x_4 + 15x_5 &= 678 \\28x_1 + 49x_2 + 4x_3 + 5x_4 + 9x_5 + 7x_6 &= 391\end{aligned}$$

x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5 va x_6 noma'lumlarni toping.

Yechish. 1-jadvalda ko'rsatilgani kabi A va b matritsa elementlarini Excel electron doskasiga kiriting. Bu jadvalda A matritsa elementlarini (A3;F8) yacheykalariga, b matritsa elementlari esa (H3;H8) yacheykalariga joylashtiriladi.

(A10; F15) yacheykalarida 6×6 o'lchovli blok ajrating va =MINVERSE(A3:F8) formulasini Ctrl va Shift klavishlarini bir vaqtda ushlagan holda kiriting.

6×1 o'lchovli (H10; H15) ustun matrisani ajratib, keyin =MMULT(A10; F15; H3; F15) satr formulasini kiritib Ctrl va Shift klavishlarini bir vaqtda bosong. Quyidagi natija hosil bo'ladi $x_1 = 5$, $x_2 = 2$, $x_3 = 12$, $x_4 = 1$, $x_5 = 8$ va $x_6 = 4$.

Bu misolda ko'p sonlar 5 birlik aniqlikda yaxlitlangan. Shunga qaramasdan, nolga juda yaqin sonlar Excel dasturida exponeta ko'rinishida ifodalangan. Masalan, 10^{17} son $-1E-17$ kabi.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1	Example 1.17							
2	A MATRIX							b
3	4	1	2	-17	-5	8		21
4	8	9	23	15	11	39		593
5	24	41	9	3	0	1		317
6	6	5	0	-1	3	-7		35
7	9	11	39	23	15	0		678
8	28	49	4	5	9	7		391
9	Inverse A^{-1}						$A^{-1} \cdot b =$	x
10	-0.0453	0.08783	0.11969	0.32077	-0.0634	-0.1339	solution	5
11	0.02431	-0.0509	-0.0504	-0.1805	0.03194	0.08268	values	2
12	0.03398	-0.0162	-1E-17	-0.0512	0.03343	-1E-17		12
13	-0.0723	0.03416	0.06457	0.05788	-0.0253	-0.0591		1
14	0.03184	-0.0257	-0.1339	-0.0156	0.0331	0.11024		8
15	0.00247	0.02302	-5E-18	-0.0118	-0.0137	4.5E-18		4

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR

1. Mike Rosser. Basic Mathematics for Economists. - London and New York, Taylor & Francis Group,
2. Applied Mathematics Journal www.scirp.org/journal/am
3. Advances in Pure Mathematics <http://www.scirp.org/journal/apm>
4. O'zbek matematika jurnali http://mathinst.uz/ozbek_matematika_jurnali.html
5. Journal of Mathematical Finance <http://www.scirp.org/journal/jmf/>
6. www.ziyonet.uz
7. <http://allmath.ru/highermath/mathanalis/>
8. <http://www.mcce.ru>, <http://lib.mexmat.ru>
9. <http://www.msu.ru/> - Московский государственный университет;
10. <http://www.nlr.ru/> - Российская национальная библиотека;
11. <http://www.nsu.ru/icem/grants/etfm/>